

Capacity Dimension	Short definition	Description of the capacities	Description related to gaps
Motivational	<i>builds awareness and desire to consider diverse values</i>	Intrinsic motivation, behaviour internally driven by a sense of meaning and interest; rewards include a sense of meaning and value, or experience of competence which, generates positive emotions within an individual	Acknowledge when motivation is an internally driven behaviour with a sense of meaning which generates positive emotions within an individual.
		Extrinsic motivation, driven by potential to earn a reward or avoid punishment.	Identify when motivation is driven by the potential to earn reward or avoid punishment.
		Cultural dimension related to local environmental attitudes, values and knowledge	Whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, it helps to define if the dimension is related to local environmental attitudes, values and knowledge.
		Economic dimension that balances benefits and costs	Whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, it helps to define if benefits and costs are balanced.
		Policy dimension addressing different framework conditions	Whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, it helps to define if the different framework conditions are addressed.
		Conflict dimension related to different interest between stakeholders, affecting the willingness of decision makers to intervene	Whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, it helps to identify if there are different interests between stakeholders, affecting the willingness of decision makers to intervene.
		Institutional dimension, related to ecosystems and institutional systems	Whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, it helps to define if there are any ecosystems or institutional systems related.
Analytical	<i>Provides knowledge and tools to analyse multiple values</i>	Power asymmetries in cognitive representations of nature could be supported through technical tools	It can help address power asymmetries in cognitive representations of nature through technical tools.
		Domination of Western science and rationality also influences the ways in which local knowledge is treated and accounted for	It helps in identifying if the domination of Western science and rationality is influencing the ways in which local knowledge is treated and accounted for.
		Transformative governance requires reconsideration of the relation between knowledge and decision-making	It can support reconsidering that there is a relation between knowledge and decision-making that is required for transformative governance.
		Scientific expertise is not required for effective and legitimate action	It allows recognizing that effective and legitimate action does not necessarily require scientific expertise.
		The relation between knowledge and decision making is not straightforward or	It helps in acknowledging that the relation between knowledge and decision making

		self-evident	is nor straightforward nor self-evident.
		Existing tools need to be adapted to generate inclusive processes for the recognition and consideration of multiple values, implying forms of scientific and non-scientific knowledge, that could be credible, legitimate and salient for all relevant stake- and knowledge-holders	It can help innovate on how existing tools can be adapted to generate inclusive processes for the recognition and consideration of multiple values, implying forms of scientific and non-scientific knowledge while being credible and salient for all relevant-stake and knowledge holders.
Bridging	<i>Brings together different ways of knowing and doing often creating new knowledge in the processes</i>	Literature on transdisciplinary and co-production offers a variety of tools and methods that can be used to organize participatory knowledge production that are able to bridge practical, local, and indigenous knowledge	It supports the use of the variety of tools and methods on the transdisciplinary and co-production literature to organize participatory knowledge production able to bridge practical, local, and indigenous knowledge.
		The application of inclusive and participatory approaches is limited and their ability to produce positive outcomes for problem solving and stakeholder empowerment depends on the presence of an enabling institutional context	It helps to enable institutional contexts for improving the application of inclusive and participatory approaches and for the production of positive outcomes for problem solving and stakeholder empowerment.
		An enabling institutional context would be able to effectively address unequal power relations between stake- and knowledge holders	It can help address unequal power relations between stake and knowledge holders by enabling institutional contexts.
Negotiation	<i>Navigates trade-offs and mainstreams into policy and practice</i>	Forcing behaviour, contending the other party	It helps in forcing behaviour or contending with the other party.
		Problem-solving, behaviour – reconciling the parties' primary interests	It helps in reconciling the parties' primary interests.
		Negotiation of meaning, that is the process through which people with different perspectives arrive at a sufficiently common understanding of a challenge or problem for their current purposes	It helps in supporting a sufficiently common understanding of a challenge or problem by different people with different perspectives for their current purposes.
		Building negotiation capacity at the individual level requires decision-makers and practitioners to be able to overcome the “negotiator's dilemma” of having to choose between promoting cooperation versus advancing own interests, to consider negotiation as a process, to reinvent the strategy of negotiation and see the value of building relationships with their counterparts	It helps in choosing between promoting cooperation versus advancing own interests, considering negotiation as a process, reinventing the strategy of negotiation and seeing the value of building relationships with their counterparts

		Improving organizational negotiation capacity requires identifying the negotiation challenges most important to the organization's success, reflecting on how effectively the organization is meeting those challenges, revising policies and staffing that affect negotiation success and building skills to increase success	It can allow identifying the negotiation challenges that are most important to the organization's success, reflecting on how effectively the organization is meeting those challenges, revising policies and staffing that affect negotiation success and building skills to increase success.
		Training and other forms of knowledge and skill-building of staff to achieve institutional change	It entails training and other forms of knowledge and skill-building of staff to achieve institutional change.
		Ensure trainees have an opportunity to use the concepts in context, offer easy access to negotiation support and have the operating procedures of the institution, both formal and informal, aligned to enable negotiators to be effective	It can help ensure that trainees have an opportunity to use the concepts in context, offer easy access to negotiation support and have the operating procedures of the institution, both formal and informal, aligned to enable negotiators to be effective.
		Capacity to negotiate for trade-offs, including having trade-off management measures in the decision-making process, such as the "trade-off decision-making tool" assists trade-offs management operationalization also needs to be enhanced	It can help negotiating trade-offs, including having trade-off management measures in the decision-making process.
		The issue of "boundary-crossing" must be tactfully addressed to promote interagency cooperation by bridging "divided terrains" to enable renegotiation and reorganization of collaborative relations and practices between and within the activity systems	It can support interagency cooperation by promoting interagency cooperation and bridging "divided terrains" to enable renegotiation and reorganization of collaborative relations and practices between and within the activity systems.
		Build institutional capacities to promote biodiversity mainstreaming in policies, by addressing the barriers and finding levers relating to institutional, motivational and means	It can help build institutional capacities to promote biodiversity mainstreaming in policies, by addressing the barriers and finding levers relating to institutional and motivational means.
Social network	<i>Stimulates learning together, act and adapt or transform</i>	Social network analysis can be used to understand joint management and the establishment of cross-scale linkages, as well as network structure supporting stability, flexibility, and innovation to increase regional resilience	Stimulates the use of social network analysis to understand joint management and the establishment of cross-scale linkages, as well as network structure supporting stability, flexibility, and innovation to increase regional resilience.
		Social learning is both the cooperation of partners. The outcome of this cooperation that occurs most efficiently through joint problem solving and reflection within learning networks can be reinforced by experiences	It promotes the cooperation of partners. The outcome of this cooperation that occurs most efficiently through joint problem solving and reflection within learning networks can be reinforced by experiences.

	<p>Social learning is posited for more broad scale use in providing multi-level governance linkages and as a basis for targeting interventions to address policy gaps or failure, but will be required to manage risk, support stakeholder analysis and resolve funding issues</p>	<p>It promotes social learning to provide multi-level governance linkages and as a basis for targeting interventions to address policy gaps or failure.</p>
<p>Social learning is posited for more broad scale use in providing multi-level governance linkages and as a basis for targeting interventions to address policy gaps or failure, but will be required to manage risk, support stakeholder analysis and resolve funding issues</p>	<p>It promotes social learning required to manage risk, support stakeholder analysis and resolve funding issues.</p>	
<p>Weaving indigenous and mainstream knowledge within science arenas is important to promote co-learning, including a “two-eyed seeing” element where people familiar with both knowledge systems uniquely combine the two in various ways that allow to meet a challenge or task at hand</p>	<p>It helps combine perspectives to meet a challenge or a task at hand by including indigenous and mainstream knowledge simultaneously.</p>	
<p>Knowledge co-production is defined as the collaborative process of bringing a plurality of knowledge sources and types together to address a defined problem and build an integrated or systems-oriented understanding of that problem</p>	<p>It helps in applying concepts such as knowledge co-production (which refers to the collaborative process of bringing a plurality of knowledge sources and types together to address a defined problem) and build an integrated or systems-oriented understanding of that problem.</p>	
<p>Five principles for effective practice of knowledge exchange, - design; represent; engage; impact; reflect and sustain - to assist researchers, decision-makers and other stakeholders working in contrasting environmental management settings to work together to co-produce new knowledge</p>	<p>It supports the co-production of new knowledge (carried out by researchers, decision-makers and other stakeholders working in contrasting environmental management settings) by applying the five principles for effective practice of knowledge exchange: design, represent, engage, impact, reflect and sustain.</p>	
<p>Co-management, which can be considered a knowledge partnership, relates to knowledge generation, bridging organizations, social learning, and the emergence of adaptive co-management</p>	<p>It can help understanding the concepts that can be applied to the same processes, such as co-management and knowledge partnership, that relate also to knowledge generation, bridging organizations, social learning, and the emergence of adaptive co-management.</p>	
<p>Adaptation, considered as responses to risks associated with the interaction of environmental hazards, is intimately associated with the concepts of vulnerability and adaptive capacity</p>	<p>It allows generating responses to risks associated with the interaction of environmental hazards such as adaptation proposals, which are also related to vulnerability and adaptive capacity.</p>	

		Recognizing adaptation as a process involves the ability to consider consequences of different adaptation options, evaluating and negotiating trade-offs, and communication among diverse groups	It allows recognizing adaptation as a process that requires the consideration of consequences of different adaptation options, evaluating and negotiating trade-offs, and communicating among diverse groups.
Governance		Related to accountability, transparency, rule of law and participation	It helps identify and address variables such as accountability, transparency, rule of law, and participation.
	<i>Create formal and informal mechanisms for a socially just governance environment</i>	Some ILK experiences have shown a lack of recognition of indigenous authority; inadequate focus on human resource development at the local level; lack of information to facilitate decisions; very little jurisdiction authority for communities to control important matters; categorization of indigenous people as disadvantaged rather than as people who have rights and responsibilities and lack of a land base or no control to traditional lands	It helps analyzing if there exists lack of recognition of indigenous authority; inadequate focus on human resource development at the local level; lack of information to facilitate decisions; enough jurisdiction authority for communities to control important matters; categorization of indigenous people as disadvantaged rather than as people who have rights and responsibilities and lack of a land base or no control to traditional lands.
		There are many tools available to set up inclusive and participatory mechanisms for capacity development and knowledge co-creation, including IPLC-led codes of ethical conduct in conservation, and tools for dialogue such as the Whakatane Mechanism	It provides tools to set up inclusive and participatory mechanisms for capacity and knowledge creation such as IPLC-led codes of ethical conduct in conservation, and tools for dialogue such as the Whakatane Mechanism.
		Legal approaches that draw inspiration from indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) and customary institutions	It provides legal approaches that can help set up inclusive participatory mechanisms for capacity development and knowledge co-creation, which can be inspired in indigenous and local knowledge as well as customary institutions.